

DEVELOPMENT OF MENTORING AND APPLICATIONS CONSELING *ONLINE (WEB)* IN SMA NEGERI 1 BALIKPAPAN

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Abstract:The Purpose of This Research is the Development of Guidance and Counseling Applications *Online(Web)* at SMAN 1 Balikpapan. The research method using descriptive method using the approach of research and development (*research and development*). Descriptive research is a research that attempts to clearly describe a phenomenon and event that occurs now, which means focusing on actual problems as they were at the time the research was conducted. Based on the research method used, namely research and development, the procedures that can be taken include the following steps: Stage, Data Collection Phase, Data Processing and Analysis Phase, Designing Phase, Validation, and Model Revision, Limited Test Phase and Revision Phase. Guidance and counseling services in SMAN 1 are not yet fully optimal, because there are limitations of time and place, so service delivery has so far been focused on students who have problems. There are still many students who have never come to the BK room, they feel awkward when visiting the BK room, and often get obstacles when consulting.

Keywords: *Guidance and Counseling, Web (online).*

INTRODUCTION

The development in the era of globalization is so rapid, making all aspects of life affected. Both in the field of education are very large changes due to the influence of IT. Nowadays, sophistication has information technology and communication lot of rapid exchange of information without any restrictions.

Balikpapan Public High School 1 is an International Standard School (RSBI) in East Kalimantan, so the system used has experienced a significant change towards a more modern and sophisticated, not only done conventionally but has been based on information technology (IT). Everyone in the school is expected to be able to use an information technology-based system to support the previous system, so that the results can be better so that the target can be achieved. In line with the development of computer technology, the interaction between counselors and the individuals they serve (counselees) is not only done through face-to-face relationships but can also be done through relationships *virtual* (virtual) through the internet, in the form of "*cybercounseling*".

One of the divisions that will use a system based on information technology is a division of guidance and counseling of students, which will be created a application *web-based (web-based)*, so that the process of guidance and counseling can be done without having to meet in person between counselors and students want to do guidance and counseling. With this new technique, the process of guidance and counseling will be more interesting, interactive and has no restrictions while still paying attention to the code of ethics of guidance and counseling.

Based on the above welding researchers intend to build a-based application *web* that can help the school to facilitate guidance and counseling for students more easily and flexibly, in

connection with the objectives, above the authors choose the title "**Development of Guidance and Counseling Applications Online (web) At SMAN 1 Balikpapan.**

The website is a collection of web pages that are interconnected and the files are interrelated. The web consists of *pages* or pages, and a collection of pages called *homepages*. The homepage is in the top position, with related pages under it. Usually every page under the homepage is called a *child page*, which contains hyperlinks to other pages on the web. (Gregorius, 2000, p: 30).

The web is one of the fastest growing internet resources. The distribution of web information is carried out through a hyperlink approach, which allows a text, image or other object to become a reference for opening other pages. Through this approach, one can obtain information by moving from one page to another. (Abdul Kadir, 2010)

According to Coupey (2001, p127), a website is a network of electronic documents called web pages, whose contents can be in the form of text, graphics, and even sound formats and video formats. These documents are integrated with hyperlinks. Hyperlinks allow users to get the desired information from one page to another using the link easily.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research method using descriptive method using the approach of research and development (*research and development*). Descriptive research is a research that attempts to clearly describe a phenomenon and event that occurs now, which means focusing on actual problems as they were at the time the research was conducted. Based on the research method used, namely research and development, the procedures that can be taken include the following steps.

a. Preparation Phase

- 1) *Need assessment*
- 2) Reviewing the literature / theoretical review and relevant research results

b. Data Collection Stage

At this stage of data collection from various sources, namely BK counselors / counselors, IT experts, students using interview guidelines, questionnaires that have been compiled and other documents.

c. Data Processing and Analysis Phase

After the data / information about the guidance and counseling program is prepared by the BK teacher / counselor then studied and studied by researchers. While the data about student needs is done by processing and analysis to find out the needs of students that can be applied in a-based counseling and guidance model *web*.

d. Stage of Designing, and Revising the Model

- 1) Designing-based guidance and counseling models based *web* on theoretical studies, results of previous studies, and results of data processing.
- 2) Revise the results of the-based guidance and counseling model based *web* on suggestions and improvements from the Bk teachers and school operators.

e. Limited Test Stage

In the limited testing phase of students to evaluate the extent to which the effectiveness and usefulness of guidance and counseling using the *web* for the benefit of students.

f. Revision Phase

In the last stage of this study a revision was carried out when a-based guidance and counseling *web* was tested which required improvement, both on the content and implementation strategy.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

RESULTS

Discussing the results of the study are explained as follows:

1. Student needs for guidance and counseling services using the *web* at Balikpapan 1 Public High School.

Analyze the needs of students by using instruments of student needs. The aspects described through the instrument are:

- a. Students' habits to use IT or *information technology*

After analyzing students' needs for-based counseling and guidance services *web*, then the description of students' habits in the field of IT or *information technology*. Obtained the average habits of students towards IT shows a high habit of 76.33%. Among them as many as 30 or as much as 100% of students have been accustomed to using the internet, then there are 28 or equal to 93.33% of students have private internet facilities (including on mobile). As many as 24 or 80% of students who do not have internet at home but utilize internet facilities at school or internet facilities elsewhere. As many as 21 or 70% of students access the internet at least once a day. As many as 30 or 100% of students are accustomed to using internet applications (*e-mail*, *chat*, *social networking*). As many as 29 or 96.67% of students feel helped if there is a-based school counseling and guidance service *web*. A total of 16 or 53.33% of students were happy to send the *Web* to teachers for guidance and counseling as a means of consultation.

2. The implementation of based Counseling Guidance Services *Web-* at Balikpapan 1 Public High School The implementation of-based counseling and guidance services is *web* carried out in stages. The aspects of needs revealed through the interview are as follows.

- a. Habits of Using the Internet

In connection with the habits of BK teachers in using the internet, provide an explanation of these conditions. The average habit of BK teachers uses the internet is very high, as many as three teachers. Where as many as three BK teachers often use the Internet. As many as 3 BK teachers have private internet facilities (including on *mobile phones*). As many as 3 BK teachers use internet facilities in schools or internet facilities elsewhere. As many as 3 BK teachers accessed the internet at least once a day. By using internet applications such as *e-mail*, *chat*, *web*, *social networking* like Facebook.

- b. The nature of-based *web*

SMA 1 guidance and counseling services has carried out guidance and counseling services using the *web*. Appendix 4 provides an explanation of these conditions. Based on attachment 4 it is known that the average BK teacher's understanding of the importance of-based counseling counseling *webservices* in schools tends to be high, as many as 3 BK teachers. Where as many as 1 BK teacher have known the term *Web counseling*. As many as 2 counselors used facilities *Web counseling* at school. All BK teachers agreed to use facilities *Web* to provide counseling guidance services at school.

3. Web-Based Guidance and Counseling Service Models in Balikpapan 1 Public High School That Match School Objective Conditions and Student Expectations

Based on objective condition analysis of students' needs for-based counseling and guidance services and existing counseling *web* guidance programs, counseling and guidance experts, and assessment more in depth about the-based guidance and counseling service model *web* from various sources, the-based guidance and counseling model *web* that is suitable to be implemented in Balikpapan 1 State Senior High School is as follows:

- a. The purpose of implementing-based guidance and counseling *web* at SMA Negeri 1 is to be able to provide services to students through the *web* regarding academic, personal-social, and career.
- b. Service content hierarchically must be able to meet the needs of students both in the academic, personal-social, and career fields.
- c. Components of-based guidance and counseling *webservices* consist of: 1) public services, in the form of providing general information for all students of Balikpapan 1 State High School displayed on the information on the web homepage; 2) responsive services, in the form of using *chaating counseling and e-mail*; 3) future planning, in the form of the availability of links to well-known universities and tutoring institutions that have collaborated with Balikpapan Public High School 1; and 4) system support, in the form of BK teacher forums where BK can share information in improving competence as a counselor, in addition to providing information relating to how to handle students, how to be friends with students, and so on goes according to need.
- d. The implementation strategy is in the form of operational standards in the use of school websites wheredisplay *web* must be considered in such a way that the needs of students in conducting-based consultation or counseling *web* can be fulfilled.
- e. Evaluations are held by polling with specific topics such as howlooks *web counseling*, how to fill information, and so on. In addition to evaluations conducted by students, evaluation was also carried out by BK teachers and IT technicians.

DISCUSSION

This section discusses the results of the per-answer research for the formulation of questions as well as the achievement of the research objectives that have been described.

1. Overview of Student Needs for Web-Based Guidance and Counseling Services at SMAN 1 Balikpapan. The results of the study show that students' habits in using *information technology* or IT are very high. This has an impact on guidance and counseling services must be able to fill students' needs for IT in this case through the *web*. So that it is appropriate for the implementation of guidance and counseling services to begin to pay attention to the use of the *web* as a medium in carrying out guidance and counseling. Based on the results of the study, it is known that the needs of students for-based counseling and guidance services *webare* covered in the fields of learning / academic, career, and social person. Therefore, if in the preparation of the program based on the ABKIN signs, the minimum service area that must be in place is learning, career and social person, then the same is the case with the service sector that must exist in-based counseling and guidance services *web*. *The website* can also be used to help counselees understand and gain access to remote counseling.
2. The Implementation of Web-Based Counseling Guidance Services That Are Running in SMAN 1 Balikpapan.

One of the guidance and counseling programs at SMA Negeri 1 Balikpapan is to conduct counseling services through the *web* for students who want to solve the problem without having to meet directly with the BK teacher. Many students want to solve the problem, but students are unable to communicate with the counselor directly for reasons of embarrassment, or because the opportunity for time and space is not appropriate to consult, and not open to express the real problem. In addition, the facilities available at SMA Negeri 1 Balikpapan support the implementation of-based counseling guidance, *web* namely providing services *online* and using the *web*. This service can be used using hotspots or *wi-fi*

facilities provided by the school. In addition, students of SMAN 1 Balikpapan have had internet habits, this is a commodity that can encourage educational creativity and innovation can be implemented one of them through-based counseling and guidance *web*. However, the guidance and counseling services in SMAN 1 are not yet fully optimal, because there are limitations of time and place, so service delivery has so far been focused on students who have problems. There are still many students who have never come to the counseling and counseling room, they feel awkward when visiting the counseling and counseling room, and often get obstacles when consulting.

The results of the study explained that students who had conducted guidance and counseling through the internet media felt very helpful. Therefore, the development of an system model *e-counseling* with media *weblog* for services counseling and guidance in general has been feasible to be implemented in SMAN 1 Balikpapan. Some schools that have implemented guidance services and through the *web* and the results obtained are very encouraging.

3. Development between conventional models with Balikpapan 1 State Senior High School an ideal model of-based counseling counselingBased on the results of the study, an overview of the ideal conditions of-based guidance and counseling models *Webservicesweb* in the new SMA Negeri 1 Balikpapan there are eight components that have been implemented from all 45 components that must be there are, among others, reviewing the needs of counselees and individuals, reviewing the latest available assessments, information and learning resources, identifying the needs of counselees and individuals that are effectively met by service sources, reviewing the content and excellent features of the *website*, reviewing examples of *websites* that have diverse features, conduct a test of fitness for use, assessresources and services current provided to the counselee, and observing and interviewing users attempted to identify the strengths and constraints in the design and integration of *thewebsite*. Therefore, to develop a-based guidance and counseling model *web*, the components that have not been implemented should be strived to be carried out so that the-based guidance and counseling *web* model can be a real model implemented in SMAN 1 Balikpapan.-based counseling *web* Ideal but factualincludes: reviewing services that effectively help counselees use available resources, identify obstacles in current resources and services effectively in meeting the needs of counselees and individuals; identify how a *website* can improve its success and reduce constraints in resources / services; approve the duties of the staff and the required budget, approve the duties of the staff and the required budget; review all content that is in accordance with professional standard practices; approvefeatures *website*; approve text display format (snippets of information, page length, memory capacity, legibility, accessible, and order of things); approve the graphic display format (effective use of icons or symbols and photography); select the *software* development and delivery of *thesite*;web create page designs (*headers*, *footers*, letters, colors, clarity of selected lines, *style sheets*, etc.); create *templates* for target clarity, clarity of needs, and information delivery; create a page and enter a link between these pages; make tools based on sources (search engine, site map, and index); conduct proper tests to use (observe users), survey target responses, staff, and related parties; choose software to monitorusage *website*; examine the needs of counselees, staff and organizations; reviewing the current sources and services provided to counselees; discuss theory and practice issues among staff to generate ideas about past and new services to help counselees and individuals use the *website*; examine the relevance of professional standards to generate ideas about the quality of services provided by counselees; introduce all staff to the features and operation of the *website*; determine how to use *websites* in service delivery; determine how a *website* can be

used with other assessments, information and learning resources; determine how counselors, professionals, and support staff can help counselees use the *website* effectively; determine how a *website* can collaborate with other service providers; determine how the *website* will be used by counselees in computers at counseling / career centers; develop procedures for scheduling counselees in using the *website* if making an appointment is used; develop plans for evaluating the effectiveness of the *website*; communicate progress with relevant parties and administrators who can provide support; develop staff training planning; train professional, paraprofessional staff and support staff; introducedesign and use *websiteto* administrators and related parties; evaluate the effectiveness of training and subsequent training plans; continue staff training as needed; identify trial users; start an experimental use system; revise the role of staff and operational procedures as needed; and continuing staff training as needed.

From-based quality guidance and counseling *web* services, students must consider the services they receive. The approach used to measure quality services must compare students' expectations before receiving services with their perceptions after the service is truly received.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the results of the analysis and discussion of conclusions that can be taken from this study are:

1. Based on the results of the study, an overview of the ideal conditions of-based guidance and counseling *web* in Balikpapan 1 State Senior High School there are eight components that have been implemented from the entire 45 components that must be . for that SMAN 1 Balikpapan will strive for the creation of-based guidance and counseling model *web* an ideal.
2. Guidance and counseling services at SMAN 1 are not yet fully optimal, because there are limitations of time and place, so service delivery has so far been focused on students who have problems. There are still many students who have never come to the BK room, they feel awkward when visiting the BK room, and often get obstacles when consulting.
3. Student interest in-based guidance and counseling *webservices* is very high, this can be seen by students feeling the comfort after using-based counseling and guidance services in *web* fact it can help students in solving student problems in the form of consultation through the *web* it can help students in solve the student's problem

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